

Biaxial Tests on the SCSC-Plate as a Deck Slab of a Trough Bridge

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The Steel-Concrete-Steel-Composite-Plate (SCSC-Plate), currently in development at Technische Universität Wien, Institute of Structural Engineering – Research Unit Steel Structures, is being researched as an innovative alternative to a thick solid steel deck slab of railway bridges. The multi-layer structure of the plate consists of two steel cover plates and a reinforced concrete core, hence the name of sandwich plate. Perforated shear connectors, welded alternately to only one of the steel cover plates work together with the concrete core to ensure the transmission of the shear flow between the cover plates.

The SCSC-Plate could function as a standalone structure in the form of a slab bridge and can also serve as the bottom flange of a trough bridge. This paper focuses on the latter application, in which the SCSC-Plate is exposed to a tensile force in the longitudinal direction of the bridge. The main research goal is the investigation of the influence of this longitudinal tensile force on the load-bearing capacity of the shear connectors. Therefore, a comprehensive series of biaxial tests, involving tensile forces in the longitudinal direction and shear forces applied to the shear connectors, was conducted on seven large-scale specimens encompassing four shear connector types. The test results provide essential insights into the behaviour of the SCSC-Plate, making a significant contribution to its overall development.

Keywords: SCSC-Plate, shear connectors, experimental investigations

1 INTRODUCTION

The replacement of old steel railway bridges with open decks by modern structures with continuous ballasted decks generally requires track structures with an extremely minimised height between the bottom edge of the structure and the top of the rail. The use of the newly developed Steel-Concrete-Steel-Composite-Plate (SCSC-Plate) can overcome many of the drawbacks associated with the current construction method, predominantly employed by the Austrian Federal Railways (ÖBB) (80-200 mm thick solid steel plate for slab bridges, 120 mm thick solid steel plate for trough bridges). These disadvantages include challenges such as the difficult availability of these plates for small order quantities and technologically demanding welded joints. The greatest challenge in the development of the SCSC-Plate is the development of a shear connector between the steel cover plates that has sufficient load-bearing capacity in ultimate and fatigue limit states.

Shear connectors play a critical role in ensuring the effective transfer of loads between steel and concrete components in composite structures. Understanding their behaviour under different loading conditions is essential for designing safe and efficient steel bridges. This study aims to assess the influence of main load-bearing action and reinforcement strategies on the performance of newly developed shear connectors through experimental investigation and comparative analysis.

2 PREVIOUS NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH

Extensive numerical simulations, as well as numerous experimental laboratory investigations on SCSC-Plate elements and small-scale specimens have been carried out to determine the load-bearing and fatigue behaviour of the plate (1). In these studies, the static and dynamic load-bearing capacity of the plate was analysed only parallel to the shear connectors (2). In other words, only the application of the plate as a slab bridge was investigated. These numerical and experimental investigations showed that the SCSC-Plate, when used as a slab bridge, has an enormously high load-bearing capacity ($P_{Rd} = 3,4 \cdot P_{Ed,ULS}$) and an extremely high ductility (3). The perforated shear connectors were identified as the most critical structural elements of the SCSC-Plate for the fatigue verification (4). Their fatigue strength has been verified in (5) and in (6).

Since the SCSC-Plate forms the bottom flange in trough bridges, the plate contributes significantly to the main load-bearing action of the bridge and thus receives a tensile force. These tensile force causes cracks in the concrete core of the plate, which are likely to occur in the areas of the dowels where the concrete cross-section is minimal. To analyse the influence of these crack formation on the load-bearing capacity of the shear connectors, a complete trough bridge with a span of 26 metres was modelled in the FE program ABAQUS (7) as an example, see *Fig 1, right*. Considering the symmetry planes, the model size is $\frac{1}{4}$ of the bridge – width approx. 2.2 m, total length approx. 14 m. The model was subjected to permanent and traffic loads (Load Model 71 in (8), load position: maximum bending moment for LM71) and then calculated using the ABAQUS/Explicit calculation algorithm. With its 8 million finite elements, the size of the model far exceeds the usual model sizes in the field of civil engineering research. This model was used to determine the strain state of the plate and the dowel forces in the shear connectors in ultimate and fatigue limit states. In addition, the model allowed a detailed analysis of the state of the concrete core during and after the crack propagation phase.

Fig. 1. Application of the SCSC-Plate as a trough bridge; top: trough bridge example; right: $\frac{1}{4}$ ABAQUS trough bridge model; left: inner structure without top plate and concrete core

The internal structure of the SCSC-Plate is shown in *Fig. 1 left*. It consists of a 15 mm thick steel top plate, a 170 mm thick reinforced concrete core and a 15 mm thick steel bottom plate, giving a total height of 200 mm. The perforated shear connectors are 20 mm thick and are welded alternately to only one of the steel cover plates. The concrete dowels are spaced 165 mm apart and are 100 mm in diameter. For more detailed information on the structural design of the plate and on the load-bearing function, see (9).

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 Development of the biaxial test specimens and the test setup

The main objective of the biaxial tests was to analyse the influence of the main load-bearing action of the bridge on the static load-bearing capacity of the shear connectors. For this purpose, a plate region close to the main girder was taken from the middle part of the bridge – see *Fig. 1 top* and *Fig. 2* – where both the dowel forces as a result of the shear force from the transverse load-bearing action of the plate and the tensile force in the plate from the longitudinal action of the bridge are maximum. The effects of bending the plate in the transverse direction were neglected as this would result in test specimens measuring the entire width of 4.5 m. Also, the effects of the bending moment in the longitudinal direction were neglected in the plate, as they are very small compared to the longitudinal tension. To simplify the test specimen, slab sections of approx. 1 m x 1 m were created and only the two beforementioned forces (longitudinal tension and shear force) were applied to the test specimen using hydraulic presses in a test frame (10).

Fig. 2. Development of the test specimen and test setup; a) Trough bridge section from the middle part of the bridge; b) Biaxial Test Specimen; c) Biaxial Test Frame

3.2 Test Phases

The test specimens were loaded in two phases. In the first phase, four of the seven specimens were subjected to a tensile force resulting from the main load-bearing action of the bridge (blue arrows in *Fig. 2b*). For this purpose, the reinforcing bars or threaded rods installed in the test specimens were anchored to the test frame on one side and to a steel girder on the opposite side. This steel girder was pushed away from the test frame using eight hydraulic presses, pulling the rebars or threaded rods and stretching the concrete cores of the test specimens. The tensile force was increased to a load level of $1.0 \cdot \text{ULS}$ (corresponding to a strain of approx. 0.8 mm/m for the trough bridge example with a span of 26 metres for the actions with LM71) and held constant for the rest of the test. A suitable support structure was used to prevent further expansion of the concrete core until the end of the tests.

In a second phase, the test specimens were loaded with a shear force orthogonal to the applied tensile force (red arrows in *Fig. 2b*). The shear force was applied by four hydraulic presses mounted between the test frame and the force application plate of the test specimens. The force application plate was welded centrally in the vertical and horizontal directions to the top plate of the test specimens (green

in Fig. 2c). On the opposite side there were two supports that held the test specimens in the direction of the shear force. The supports were located at the height of the bottom plate of the test specimens (blue in Fig. 2b). Due to the vertical eccentricity between the shear presses and the supports, it was also necessary to hold the test specimens in a vertical direction. This was achieved using steel girders (not shown in Fig. 2c for better visibility) above both the force application plate and the top plate of the test specimens, which were anchored vertically with threaded rods in a clamping field (solid base plate) under the test setup. To ensure that the specimens could slide in the horizontal plane during both phases, a Teflon-silicone-Teflon sheet was placed under the test specimen. After completing three ULS-cycles, the shear force was applied until the load-bearing capacity of the test specimen was reached or the available measuring distances were reached.

3.3 Types of shear connectors tested

During the biaxial tests, specimens were fabricated and tested using different types of shear connectors. In three of the test specimens the shear transfer between the steel cover plates (top and bottom plate) is achieved by perforated shear connectors welded alternately to only one of the cover plates at 500 mm intervals. These are referred to as Type 1 test specimens, see Fig. 3. This type of shear connector – without reinforcement – represents the previously investigated design variant of the SCSC-Plate in (1–6).

The second type of shear connector also uses perforated dowel strips, but instead of being equidistant, they are arranged in pairs with a centre-to-centre distance of 100 mm (one pair of shear connectors per meter of plate length). With this arrangement, the resulting concrete compression struts between the shear connectors are much shorter and have a much smaller angle to the connectors (approx. 20° vs. approx. 45°). Both of these features can have an influence on the load-bearing behaviour of the shear connectors if the concrete core is cracked in the dowel area due to the main load-bearing action.

Type 1: Perforated shear connectors with equidistant spacing of 500 mm

Type 2: Perforated shear connector pairs with a centre-to-centre distance of 100 mm

Type 3: Perforated shear connector pairs supplemented with headed studs

Type 4: Perforated and headed stud shear connector pairs

Fig. 3. Investigated shear connector types

The third type of shear connector is a kind of mixture of perforated dowel strips and strips with headed studs. As with Type 2, the shear connectors are arranged in pairs. However, instead of every second hole, a headed stud is welded onto the shear connector. These headed studs are offset on the two neighbouring strips so that the headed studs of one connector can be guided through the openings of the other connector. In this way, the two connectors are interlocked. The concrete is likely to be held in the dowels by the interlocking studs. It is expected that the concrete will crack from the head of

the studs towards the shear connectors in a cone shape when the tensile load is applied. This means that the concrete core between the cracks, and therefore in the dowel areas, should be free of cracks so that the shear force can be transferred without problems, despite the strain from the main load-bearing action.

The fourth type of shear connector is similar to the third. However, all the headed studs are welded on one side, which means that one of the strips has only holes – a perforated shear connector – and the other strip, to which all the headed studs are welded, is continuous across the entire width of the plate. This means that once the static friction between the concrete core and the steel cover plates has been overcome, no tensile force is transferred to the concrete core. Only a gap of 0.8 mm is likely to occur on the studless side of the continuous strip. This arrangement therefore separates the location of the crack, in this case the gap next to the continuous strip, from the location of the shear force transfer, leaving the concrete free from cracking and strain and ensuring an undisturbed shear transfer mechanism.

3.4 Biaxial tests

Firstly, to represent the conditions of a slab bridge application, a specimen with a Type 1 shear connector was tested without the tensile force applied, see TS1/1 in *Table 1*. To realistically simulate the conditions in a slab bridge, namely the symmetry in the centres of the dowel bars, the elongation of the concrete core in the shear phase was prevented. Secondly, to analyse the influence of concrete cracking in the dowel area in the trough bridge application, a specimen was tested with the same type of shear connector but with the tensile force first applied (TS1/2). The tensile force was applied to this test specimen using threaded rods inserted into the edge area of the concrete core of the specimen. Finally, to analyse the influence of reinforcement, a third Type 1 specimen was tested, reinforced with $\varnothing 20$ main rebars per dowel and additional $\varnothing 10$ rebars perpendicular to them (TS1/3), see *Fig. 4*. The tension was applied directly to the main rebars of the specimen.

The one specimen with a Type 2 shear connector was also reinforced with the same rebars as in TS1/3. There were two specimens with Type 3 shear connectors, one with and one without a tension phase, TS3/1 and TS3/2 respectively. Since in an SCSC-Plate with a Type 4 shear connector no tensile force is transferred to the concrete core, no tensile force was applied to the one Type 4 specimen, only a strain of the concrete core by 0.8 mm/m (corresponds to a load level 1.0·ULS) was allowed in the shear phase. For details of each test, see *Table 1*.

Table 1. Details of the biaxial test specimens and the test procedures

Name	Type of shear connector	Represented bridge length in terms of		Reinforcement	Application	Phases		Elongation of the concrete core allowed in	
		Shear transfer	Concrete core elongation			Tension	Shear	Tension phase	Shear phase
TS1/1	perforated shear connector with equidistant spacing	1 m	1 m	-	slab bridge	-	✓	-	-
TS1/2				-	trough bridge	✓	✓	✓	-
TS1/3				✓	trough bridge	✓	✓	✓	-
TS2/1	perforated shear connector pairs	1 m	2 m	✓	trough bridge	✓	✓	✓	-
TS3/1	perforated shear connector pairs	1 m	2 m	-	slab bridge	-	✓	-	-
TS3/2	supplemented with headed studs			-	trough bridge	✓	✓	✓	-
TS4/1	perforated and headed stud shear connector pairs	1 m	2 m	-	trough bridge	-	✓	-	✓

The challenge in designing the specimens was to find suitable specimen shapes that would allow the inner concrete core to be stretched in the main load-bearing direction to the desired strain state without having to pull the steel cover plates along with it. The solution for the Type 1 specimens was to cut the bottom plate in half under the top shear connector so that only the concrete core (and reinforcement if present) needed to be stretched to separate the two bottom shear connectors at the edge of the specimen. As this test specimen represent one metre bridge length, the tension in the first phase was applied until a total elongation of the concrete core of 0.8 mm was achieved. After that a suitable support structure was used to prevent any further expansion of the concrete core in the shear phase.

The Type 2 and Type 3 specimens represents a two-metre bridge length in terms of the maximal concrete elongation. The strain-distributing effect of the main rebars in test specimen VK2/1 was neglected on the safe side. Therefore, the tension in the specimens TS 2/1 and 3/2 was applied until a total elongation of the concrete core of 1.6 mm was achieved.

The top shear connectors in the centre of the specimens and the surrounding concrete core were tested in Type 1 specimens, but not the bottom shear connectors and the concrete core at the edge of the specimen. To eliminate shear failure at the bottom shear connectors, the edge areas were additionally reinforced with short $\varnothing 10$ rebars in the longitudinal direction and with $\varnothing 26$ rebars welded directly to the dowel bar between the dowels, acting as additional shear connectors. For all other test specimen types, the entire shear connector was tested, including the concrete in the shear transfer area.

Fig. 4. Detailed view of the specimen TS1/3 and forces in the test phases

3.5 Tests Results

To measure the deformation of the specimens, 23 inductive displacement transducers were used, 8 of which were used to measure the relative displacement between the top and bottom plates. From 8 absolute measurements, 4 relative measurements were calculated, and the 4 resulting curves were averaged. The support forces were measured on both supports using load cells. The sum of the two

measurements was divided by the number of dowels loaded in the specimens. The resulting shear forces per dowel versus the relative displacement of the steel cover plates diagrams of all test specimens are compared in *Fig. 5*.

Influence of the main load-bearing action on the shear connector Type 1:

Compering the results of TS1/1 (without tension) and TS1/2 (with tension) indicate that TS1/2 exhibits significantly lower capacity and stiffness compared to TS1/1. The failure mode observed in TS1/2 involves the complete shearing of the concrete dowels due to the development of concentrated cracks in the dowel area, leading to a substantial decrease in shear capacity.

Effect of the reinforcement in the shear connector Type 1:

An analysis of the results of TS1/2 (without reinforcement) and TS1/3 (with reinforcement) reveals that TS1/3 demonstrates significantly higher load-carrying capacity. In particular, TS1/3 withstood 100 load cycles at a level of 4.70 ULS without failure. Further load escalation was limited by the capacity of the hydraulic presses and load-bearing capacity of the test frame, emphasizing the effectiveness of reinforcement in enhancing structural performance. The effect of the main reinforcement was certainly not to concentrate the concrete cracks exclusively in the area of the dowel, but to distribute them somewhat along the entire width of the test specimen, thus reducing the crack widths. This crack spreading effect of the main reinforcement therefore had a very positive effect on the shear capacity of the perforated shear connector.

Fig. 5. Test results

Influence of the main load-bearing action on the shear connector Type 3:

Comparative evaluation between TS3/1 (without tension) and TS3/2 (with tension) shows slightly lower capacity for VK3/2. Conclusion: As expected, the shear transfer area probably remained uncracked. However, it is worth noting that the sound of discrete concrete cracking in this specimen during the tensile phase was surprisingly loud.

Comparison of all tested designs for the trough bridge applications:

Of all the specimens tested with tension (TS1/3, TS2/1, TS3/2 and TS4/1), TS1/3 has the highest shear capacity, making it the preferred choice for trough bridge applications.

Further considerations:

It can be assumed that neglecting the strain-distributing effect of the main reinforcement in specimen TS2/1 was too conservative (see section 3.2), which is why the specimen was overstretched up to a load level of about $2.0 \cdot \text{ULS}$, and this is the reason for the surprisingly low load-bearing capacity of this specimen.

After 100 load cycles on TS1/3, the lateral supports were removed so that the lateral component of the concrete compression diagonals was not supported. With this weakening, it was possible to achieve failure of the test specimen. *Fig. 6. left* shows the crack pattern in the concrete core under the top plate of TS1/3 after opening the specimen. A crack pattern corresponding to a shear failure is clearly visible. The angle of the crack to the shear connector is slightly smaller than expected (approx. 27° vs. approx. 45°). After removing the concrete from the main rebars, their deformation is revealed. It is evident that the rebar running through dowel one is bent more concentrated than the rebar in dowel five. This observation corresponds to the crack pattern due to the shear failure of the concrete core.

Fig. 6. Opened specimen TS1/3; left: crack pattern in the concrete core; right: deformation of the main reinforcement

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This paper presents 4 types of shear connectors for application in steel-concrete composite structures, with the particular intention of using these shear connectors in trough bridges with SCSC-Plate. Due to the main load-bearing action of the trough bridges, the plate is subjected to a longitudinal tension in addition to the shear force and the bending moment in the transverse direction. As part of an FFG (The Austrian Research Promotion Agency) research project, seven biaxial tests were carried out to investigate the load-bearing behaviour of the shear connectors for this application of the SCSC-Plate. It was found that the shear capacity of the perforated bars was significantly lower due to the main load bearing action. Furthermore, the significant benefit of reinforcing the perforated shear connectors with rebars was verified. This shear connector type had a significantly greater shear capacity than all other tested variants. This makes the perforated shear connector with equidistant spacing with reinforcement the preferred choice of shear connector for trough bridge applications.

These experimental results highlight the significant influence of the main load-bearing action and the reinforcement on the behaviour of shear connectors in steel-concrete composite structures. Understanding these factors is essential for the design of robust and resistant composite structures, particularly in bridge construction applications. Further research should investigate additional parameters and configurations, with particular emphasis on the fatigue limit state, to improve the efficiency and reliability of shear connectors in steel construction practice.

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REFERENCES

1. **Hermann, Paul.** Tragfunktionsanalyse und rechnerische Modellbildung einer neuartigen Sandwich-Verbundplatte (SCSC- Platte) als Fahrbahndeck für Eisenbahnbrücken. s.l. : Dissertation, Technische Universität Wien, 2013.
2. **Steurer, Marlene und Fink, Josef.** Weiterführende Forschung zur neuartigen Sandwich Verbundplatte. *Weiterführende Forschung zur neuartigen Sandwich Verbundplatte als Fahrbahnplatte für Eisenbahnbrücken.* 2012, pp. 1-135.
3. **Steurer, M.; Petraschek, T.; Fink, J.** Development of an innovative sandwich plate for trough-type railway bridges. s.l. : Steel Construction, Vol.9, No. 3, ISBN 1867-0520, 2016.
4. **Takács, P.; Fink, J.** Neuartige Sandwichfahrbahnplatte für Eisenbahnbrücken - Analyse des Ermüdungsverhaltens der Lochdübelleiste anhand des Kerbdehnungskonzeptes. *Ernst & Sohn, Stahlbau 86. Jahrgang, Heft 5, S. 441 - 451.* 2017.
5. **Takács, Patrik and Fink, Josef.** Neuartige Sandwichfahrbahnplatte für Eisenbahnbrücken - Experimentelle Untersuchungen zur Ermüdungsfestigkeit der Lochdübelleiste. *Ernst & Sohn, Stahlbau 88, H. 6, S. 586 - 593.* 2019.

6. **Takács, Patrik.** *Analyse des Ermüdungsverhaltens der SCSC-Platte (Dissertation).* Institut für Tragkonstruktionen - Stahlbau, TU Wien, Wien, Österreich : s.n., 2018.
7. **Dassault Systemes.** Abaqus/CAE SIMULIA 2022.
<https://www.3ds.com/products/simulia/abaqus> : s.n.
8. **ÖNORM EN 1991-2.** Eurocode1: Einwirkungen auf Tragwerke - Teil 2: Verkehrslasten auf Brücken. s.l. : Österreichisches Normungsinstitut, 01.08.2004.
9. **Palotás, Bálint, Takács, Patrik and Fink, Josef.** Simulation of the SCSC plate with a spring framework model including the effects of inelastic slip. *Steel Construction.* 2021, 2, pp. 83-94.
10. **Spreitzer-Gröbner, Sebastian.** Dokumentation und Auswertung von Versuchen im Zusammenhang mit dem Forschungsthema SCSC-Platte. s.l. : Diploma Thesis, Technische Universität Wien, 2022.